

Table 5. Professional and patient barriers to offering psychological services for food allergy as reported by psychologists (N=34)

Professional barriers to offering services	N	%
Funding	28	82.4
Staff capacity	19	55.9
Clinic time	13	38.2
Staff training	11	32.4
Lack of availability of psychological services or clinic space	10	29.4
Perception of the importance of psychology	6	17.6
Lack of physician understanding of services offered by psychologists	6	17.6
Lack of applicants for advertised posts	4	11.8
Lack of appointable applicants for advertised posts	3	8.8
Do not see enough to warrant allocating more time	1	2.9
No role or position available	1	2.9
Patient barriers to offering services	N	%
Referral pathways	18	52.9
Timely access	14	41.2
Family perceptions of importance of psychological services	12	35.3
Distance to travel	4	11.8
Family's cultural beliefs	2	5.9
Language barriers	2	5.9
Funding, lack of dedicated service	2	5.9
Awareness of psychological approaches and services	1	2.9
Staff capacity	1	2.9
Stigma	1	2.9
Paediatricians not referring patients	1	2.9
Knowledge that psychology services exist	1	2.9